

TECHNOLOGIES FOR TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS TO ORGANIZE INDEPENDENT EDUCATION WITH THE HELP OF VIRTUAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: this article discusses the importance of organizing independent work in the preparation of future teachers

Key words: independent work, creative work, need, socio-pedagogical activity.

Today, in the training of future specialists, one of the most important directions is to meet the educational needs of individuals and society, to optimize professional training. The main characteristic of continuing professional training is the adherence to the principle of follow-up, relying on traditions to achieve educational goals.

The reform of the education system in our republic is expected at the level of state policy, ensuring that our children acquire modern knowledge and skills in conditions suitable for world standards, and that they grow up to be physically and spiritually mature people, to realize their abilities, talents, and intellectual skills. great work is being done to develop the feelings of loyalty and devotion to the motherland in the hearts of our youth.

Conducting independent creative activity in the training of future students in pedagogic higher education institutions is an important factor in improving the quality of personnel training. It is possible to create a foundation for independent creative performance of assignments and tasks by students using problem-based interviews (interviews with the help of investigative questions) from the subjects of "Folk Crafts and Artistic Design", "Technology of Product Preparation", "Technical Creativity and Design". the purpose of education is considered.

Independent education students:

- manifestation of personal, professional, individual characteristics;
- formation of knowledge, skills, qualifications;
- planning knowledge of general technical and special subjects;
- to be able to use it consciously to organize and control learning tasks;
- lays the foundation for the development of creative abilities.

The organization of independent education in the preparation of young students is a holistic pedagogical process, which is carried out in the following order:

- to clarify students' understanding of independent education, to analyze theoretical and practical knowledge acquisition activities, to provide them with information about the socio-pedagogical importance of independent education based on the study of independent education skills and qualifications;
- to study the desire of students to receive independent education and the psychological factors affecting it, to develop the content of independent education;
- determining the workload and time standards for independent education in the auditorium and outside the auditorium based on the developed content of independent education;
- selection of organizational forms, effective methods and means of independent education for the purpose of implementation of the didactic process;
- taking into account the interest and needs of students in independent education for the purpose of education, developing tasks, developments, recommendations on specific topics;
- development of criteria for determining the level of formation of students' skills and qualifications of independent education;
- organization and implementation of independent education of students;
- assessment of the level of formation of students' independent learning skills and qualifications.

In the national model of personnel training: "... to realize the national model of personnel training aimed at forming a well-rounded person who can adapt to the

modern changing society, who understands his duty to society, state and family, which allows to consciously choose and acquire education and professional programs the need to create social-economic, legal, psychological-pedagogical conditions of withdrawal" was determined.

Therefore, on the basis of the above-mentioned algorithm for organizing students' independent education, if attention is paid to the organization of independent education in the subjects of "Folkcraft and artistic design", "Technology of product preparation", "Technical creativity and design", future students will develop their personal, professional, individual conditions are created for them to show their characteristics and express their opinions freely.

Competency approach in education is similar to current approaches of person-centered education, because it can be implemented and evaluated in a specific demand process that applies to a student's personality and performs a specific set of actions.

Competence is a requirement for the educational training of a specialist necessary to carry out effective activities in a certain field.

Competence is the acquisition of competences related to the subject of activity by a person.

Based on the above, we have given our working definition of competence. Competence is a person's ability to interact with each other, including personal relationships and the subject of activity.

Learning competence ensures the effectiveness of the development of professional and special competences, which allows to consider its development as a priority task of modern education.

Learning competence occupies a priority place in a certain part of the competences of a person, which ensures that a person occupies the world of diverse and diverse cultures.

In our opinion, cognitive competence is the main competence aimed at expanding knowledge, mastering methods of cognitive (cognitive) activity,

formation of certain knowledge and skills in educational activities, development of creative thinking, and independence in learning activities.

For this reason, we defined the learning competence of future vocational education students as the acquisition of special competencies that form the theoretical knowledge, practical skills and skills necessary for independent learning activities.

We believe that it is necessary to acquire the following skills as criteria for improving learning competence:

- the ability to organize the purpose and its possibilities, to explain its purpose;
- formation of cognitive tasks and introduction of hypotheses;
- analyzing his learning activity;
- acquiring knowledge independently;
- implementation of reflection (reflection) in learning activities;
- evaluate their learning activities;
- oral and written presentation of research results.

The educational process is focused on the development of a person capable of fulfilling the interests of the state, the interests of society and personal interests, the implementation of the educational function of education for positive socialization, taking into account the unique characteristics of the individual and the cultural traditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the universal human talents. .

Many pedagogues reveal the uniqueness of professional education in the restoration of professional pedagogical competence and develop new approaches to modeling and researching various aspects of pedagogical activity and personality. In our opinion, this will make significant changes to the content of the professional competence of future vocational education students and correspond to the demands of society, social environment and the specific field of professional-pedagogical activity.

Offers:

1. Formation of professional competences in the process of professional-pedagogical training should be carried out not only with traditions, but also with the introduction of new educational technologies, using innovative forms, methods and tools that ensure not effective implementation of new activities, but their planning.

2. Improving the management of vocational education - transferring the issue of management and control of vocational education institutions to higher education institutions. Strengthening cooperation with higher education institutions.

3. Improving the quality of vocational education - involving leading professors-teachers of higher educational institutions, organizing skill classes with their participation, working on elimination of deficiencies through exchange of ideas among teachers.

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